

Cripping the Classics: Disabled Women Reclaim *The Ugly Duckling* and *Rapunzel*

Soma Biswas

Junior Research Fellow, Central University of South Bihar, SH-7, Gaya- Panchanpur Road, Village- Karhara, Post- Fatehpur, P.S- Tekari, District- Gaya, India;
Somaapc1998@gmail.com

Dr. Arpana Jha

Assistant Professor, Central University of South Bihar, SH-7, Gaya- Panchanpur Road, Village- Karhara, Post- Fatehpur, P.S- Tekari, District- Gaya, India;
arpanajha@cusb.ac.in

Accepted version published on 1st May 2026

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19952610>

ABSTRACT

Disability Studies questions cultural ideas that treat disability as a problem or defect that needs to be fixed. Crip theory builds on this approach by challenging able-bodied norms and understanding disability as an identity and a source of agency rather than limitation. This paper explores how disabled women retell *The Ugly Duckling* and *Rapunzel* in *And They Lived... Ever After: Disabled Women Retell Fairy Tales*, and how these retellings reshape familiar fairy tales into stories of empowerment. *The Ugly Duckling* becomes a story about resilience and belonging instead of shame. In contrast, *Rapunzel* is reimagined as an active character who turns confinement into a path toward self-discovery and connection with others. Drawing on Alison Kafer's ideas about the politics of disability, the paper argues that these retellings challenge ableist and gendered assumptions and create new ways of imagining agency, community, and transformation.

Keywords: Disability Studies; Crip Theory; Fairy Tales; Gender; Retellings

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

Fairy tales are often treated as harmless stories we grew up with, something simple and familiar. However, they do a lot more work than they are usually given credit for. Over time, these stories shape how we learn to think about beauty, goodness, gender, and even bodies themselves. The worlds of fairy tales are full of patterns that repeat again and again: beautiful girls are rewarded, "ugly" or different bodies are punished. Happy endings almost always depend on some physical change. As Jack Zipes observes, fairy tales "carry the values of the culture from which they emerge," quietly reinforcing beliefs about normality, goodness, and success (34).

Disability is represented in these stories in very limited ways. Most often, it does not appear as a lived experience at all, but as a symbol. Bodies that look or move differently are shown as cursed, broken, or morally suspect, and the story only revolves once those bodies are fixed, transformed, or removed. As Maria Tatar notes, fairy tales repeatedly suggest that "deformity is a visual sign of internal deficiency," a lesson that naturalises ableist assumptions while obscuring the everyday realities of disabled lives (65). When this happens again and again, it becomes difficult to imagine disabled lives as ordinary, complex, or even possible within these narrative worlds. This is where Disability Studies becomes useful. Rather than seeing disability as an individual problem or a personal tragedy, the field understands it as something shaped by social structures, cultural attitudes, and power relations. Scholars like Rosemarie Garland-Thomson, Lennard J. Davis, and Tobin Siebers have shown how deeply ideas about "normal" bodies are embedded in cultural representation. Garland-Thomson's idea of the "normative gaze" helps explain how some bodies are treated as standard while others are constantly marked as deviant, while Davis traces how the very idea of normalcy developed historically rather than existing naturally. Seen this way, disability is not just a medical category but a way of reading the world. It highlights how certain bodies are valued, and others are excluded. Literature matters here because stories shape what we think is possible. If disabled characters only appear as objects of pity or as problems to be solved, then the imaginative space available to disabled lives remains narrow and restrictive.

Crip theory pushes these ideas further. Building on Disability Studies, it examines how ableism intersects with gender, sexuality, desire, and ideas about the future. Robert McRuer's use of the word 'crip,' much like the reclamation of "queer," deliberately unsettles the idea that normal bodies are stable or natural. Crip theory

asks what happens when disabled bodies are placed at the centre of stories instead of being pushed to the edges. Alison Kafer takes this further in *Feminist, Queer, Crip* by questioning futures that assume disabled people will be cured, corrected or simply no longer exist. Against this, she argues for "crip futures" that treat disabled lives as livable, valuable, and worth imagining.

To crip a text, then, is to read against these assumptions. It means questioning stories that treat cure as the only possible happy ending or frame bodily difference as a problem to be solved. Fairy tales, which rely heavily on transformation and closure, are especially vulnerable to this kind of re-reading. Contemporary fairy-tale retellings offer a useful space for this work. Retellings are not just modern versions of old stories; they are ways of talking back to the originals. Writers have long used fairy-tale rewritings to challenge sexist, heteronormative, or colonial ideas, but disability-focused retellings have received much less attention.

Moreover, *They Lived...Ever After: Disabled Women Retell Fairy Tales* is important in this context. Written by disabled women, the collection refuses the familiar fairy-tale logic that happiness must come after cure or bodily transformation. Disability in these stories is not erased or corrected. Instead, it shapes how characters understand themselves and how they relate to others. The retellings of *The Ugly Duckling* and *Rapunzel* are especially revealing. Both original tales revolve around bodily difference, confinement, and change, which makes them easy to read through a crip lens. Anderson's *The Ugly Duckling* ends suffering only once the body changes, while *Rapunzel* confines its heroine and limits her agency. In contrast, the retellings by Priyangee Guha and Soumita Basu resist these narrative patterns. Disability in their stories is not something to be overcome but something that exists as part of life.

This paper argues that these retellings use Crip Theory to rethink disability as a source of agency, connection, and possibility. Drawing on Alison Kafer's political model of disability, the analysis shows how these stories move away from cure-based endings, emphasising interdependence, and imagine futures that do not depend on becoming "normal." More broadly, rewriting these fairy tales becomes a political act in itself. By telling these stories differently, disabled women claim space within a genre that has long excluded them and insist on futures where disabled people are not pushed aside but allowed to remain.

Theoretical Framework

This paper draws primarily on Disability Studies as both its critical grounding and its way of reading texts. The field developed out of political activism in the 1970s and was later shaped by scholars such as Lennard J. Davis, Rosemarie Garland-Thomson, and Susan Wendell. One of its central interventions is to question the assumption that disability is a self-evident biological condition. Instead, Disability Studies asks how disability comes to be understood through social norms, cultural narratives, and relations of power. Seen from this perspective, literary texts do not simply mirror bodily difference; they help produce the meanings attached to it. Fairy tales are particularly revealing here. They rely heavily on familiar narrative patterns—lack and excess, beauty and monstrosity, punishment and transformation—and these patterns often hinge on bodily difference. For instance, characters whose bodies fail to conform to dominant norms are frequently isolated, mocked, or put on trial until they are either transformed or removed from the narrative altogether. Reading fairy tales through Disability Studies makes it possible to notice how such patterns normalise able-bodiedness while presenting exclusions as natural or deserved. Feminist disability forms another key strand of the paper's approach. Disabled women occupy a position shaped by overlapping pressures: gendered expectations, ideals of beauty, and assumptions about care, dependence, and passivity. Bodies that are marked as disabled tend to sit uneasily within cultural narratives that prize youth, symmetry, and self-control. In fairy tales, this often surfaces in the contrast between the passive, beautiful heroine and other female figures whose bodies are coded as excessive, unruly, or threatening. When disability intersects with these gendered expectations, bodily difference is more likely to be framed as a moral or emotional failure rather than as a neutral variation.

Garland-Thomson's concept of "narrative prosthesis" is useful in thinking through these issues. It draws attention to how disabled bodies are frequently used to serve narrative ends— as symbols, metaphors, or problems to be resolved— rather than being represented as complex lived experiences. A familiar example can be seen in stories where a character's bodily difference exists primarily to motivate the emotional growth of others or to mark the story's conflict, disappearing once narrative closure is achieved. By centring disabled women's voices, this paper attempts to move away from such representational shortcuts and to approach disability as a legitimate site of knowledge and subjectivity.

Crip Theory adds a further layer to the analysis by challenging the assumption of compulsory able-bodiedness. Drawing on the work of Robert McRuer, "crip" is understood here not simply as a reclaimed label, but as a critical stance. From this

perspective, ability appears not as a natural state but as something that must be constantly produced and reinforced, including through narrative repetition. Two key concepts from Crip Theory are particularly relevant to this study. The first is crypting the text, which involves reading against dominant interpretations to expose ableist logic and unsettle familiar narrative resolutions. The second is crip reclamation, a process through which disability is reimagined not as lack or failure but as a potential source of agency, creativity, and resistance. In readings of *The Ugly Duckling* and *Rapunzel*, Crip Theory allows for a reconsideration of bodies that have historically been framed as abnormal, cursed, or incomplete. Rather than treating transformation as a moment of narrative "success," this approach draws attention to what is lost or silenced when bodily difference must be erased for the story to end well. It also opens up space for imagining versions of these stories that do not depend on cure, normalisation, or bodily correction. Adaptation theory supports the paper's attention to contemporary rewritings of fairy tales. Linda Hutcheon's understanding of adaptation as an interpretive and creative act allows these retellings to be read as meaningful engagements with tradition rather than as secondary or derivative texts. When disabled women rewrite fairy tales, they are not only revising familiar plots; they are questioning the values and assumptions that have long shaped the genre.

Methodology

This paper adopts a qualitative and interpretive research approach grounded in literary analysis. It primarily relies on close reading to examine how disability is represented and reimagined in contemporary fairy-tale retellings. Close reading enables attention to narrative structure, characterisation, and language, allowing the analysis to move beyond surface-level themes and engage with the underlying ideological assumptions embedded within the texts. The study focuses on selected retellings from *And They Lived... Ever After: Disabled Women Retell Fairy Tales*, specifically Priyangee Guha's reinterpretation of *The Ugly Duckling* and Soumita Basu's *Rapunzel and the People of Companara*. These texts have been chosen because they directly engage with questions of bodily difference, confinement, transformation, and belonging; central concerns within both fairy-tale traditions and disability discourse.

The analysis follows a comparative framework, placing these contemporary retellings in dialogue with their canonical counterparts. This comparison enables identification of how dominant narrative patterns, such as transformation as resolution, cure as closure, and dependence on able-bodied norms, are resisted or reworked.

The theoretical lens guiding this study draws from Disability Studies and Crip Theory, particularly the work of Alison Kafer and Robert McRuer. Concepts such as the social model of disability, compulsory able-bodiedness, and crip futurity are used as analytical tools rather than as abstract frameworks. In addition, the paper employs what may be described as a "crip reading" practice- reading against normative assumptions in order to expose ableist logic and to foreground alternative ways of understanding embodiment, agency and relationality. The aim is not only to interpret the texts, but to examine how they intervene in dominant cultural narratives and expand the imaginative possibilities available to disabled lives.

Discussion: Priyangee Guha's *The Ugly Duckling*

Priyangee Guha's retelling of *The Ugly Duckling* moves away from the familiar idea that bodily change is the key to happiness or acceptance. Unlike Andersen's original tale, where suffering ends only when the duckling becomes a swan, Guha's version is less interested in physical transformation as redemption. In the original story, beauty and belonging arrive together, but only after the body is corrected. Difference is something to endure until it disappears. Guha's retelling unsettles this way of thinking. Kaali is not rejected because her body is inherently wrong, but because those around her do not know how to read difference except through an ableist lens. Her exclusion feels social rather than natural. The story suggests that what hurts Kaali is not her body itself, but the constant judgment, comparison, and expectation placed upon it. In this sense, the narrative aligns closely with the social model of disability, showing how marginalisation is produced by attitudes and perceptions rather than by physical limitations.

What is especially striking is the story's refusal to treat transformation as the obvious or necessary solution. Although Kaali is eventually recognised as a swan, this moment does not feel like a magical correction of something broken. There is no sense that her body suddenly becomes acceptable. Instead, the narrative implies that Kaali was always whole, even when she was not seen that way. What shifts is not her body, but the meanings attached to it by others and, gradually, by herself. This approach echoes Alison Kafer's critique of cure-focused narratives, which often frame disability as a problem that must be resolved rather than an identity that can be lived.

Kaali's journey can also be read through the idea of crip time. The story does not rush toward an ideal ending or a clear moment of arrival. Things unfold slowly and unevenly. Rather than moving toward bodily perfection or social approval, the narrative focuses on self-recognition. Progress, if it can be called that, is internal rather

than visible. This challenges the assumption that growth must always follow a linear path toward normalisation.

By reworking the original fairy tale through a disabled perspective, Guha also reshapes ideas of beauty and belonging. Beauty is no longer tied to looking a certain way or fitting into a predetermined ideal. It begins to emerge through resilience, acceptance, and relationships. The story resists the familiar fairy-tale notion that suffering becomes meaningful only when it leads to physical change. Instead, it insists that disabled lives have value even without transformation or cure. Through this retelling, *The Ugly Duckling* becomes less a story about shame and more a story about survival and self-understanding. Kaali's experience draws attention to the quiet but persistent violence of normative judgment. By centring a disabled female protagonist who is not erased, fixed, or perfected, Guha challenges the fairy-tale tradition's long reliance on bodily perfection as the condition for happiness.

Soumita Basu's *Rapunzel and the People of Companara*

Basu's *Rapunzel and the People of Companara* opens with a different kind of image than the familiar fairy tale. Rapunzel is not introduced primarily through isolation or enchantment, but through movement. She uses a wheelchair, and the text does not treat this as either a tragedy or a metaphor that needs explanation. It is simply there, shaping how she moves through space and how space responds to her. From the start, this shifts the focus away from waiting and rescue, which dominate the classical version of the tale. In the traditional Rapunzel story, confinement produces passivity. Rapunzel waits in the tower, and escape becomes possible only through the intervention of the prince. Even her long hair, often romanticised, serves as a means of access for others. Basu's refuses this logic. Rapunzel is observant and alert to the social world around her. She is not positioned as incomplete or suspended in time. Her wheelchair does not symbolise lack; it is simply part of how she lives in her body.

The replacement of Rapunzel's hair with a black silk rope makes this refusal especially visible. The rope does not lower her into freedom. Instead, it allows her to pull others up, including the prince. This reversal is not dramatic or announced as empowerment. It happens almost matter-of-factly. When the prince questions her strength, Rapunzel responds, "I can't work because of my defect in my legs, but I do have very strong arms" (Basu 26). The line is striking precisely because it does not attempt to soften or reframe disability. Rapunzel names her impairment and, at the same time, names what her body can do. Strength here is not inspirational or exceptional; it is practical. The difficulty Rapunzel faces in *Companara* is not constant

immobility but restricted access. The roads are uneven and poorly designed, making movement difficult in ways that have little to do with her wheelchair itself. The story makes this clear without turning it into a lesson. It becomes even more apparent when the prince offers to carry her. Rapunzel refuses: "I don't want to be carried. I don't like being carried" (Basu 29). This refusal matters because it pushes against a familiar narrative of care. Being carried would solve the immediate problem, but it would also reinforce dependence. Rapunzel's discomfort suggests that inclusion cannot rely on gestures that erase autonomy.

As Rapunzel moves through the province, her presence exposes the limits of Companara's social arrangements. The problem is not framed as personal misfortune but as a structural oversight. When changes are eventually made to make the region wheelchair accessible, the shift does not read as generosity or moral growth. It feels necessary, even obvious in hindsight. Disability here functions less as an individual condition and more as a point through which social organisation is questioned. By the end of the narrative, Rapunzel is no longer presented as a solitary figure. She appears alongside other disabled people, forming a visible community. This moment does not conventionally resolve the story, but it does interrupt the pattern of isolation that often defines disabled characters in fairy tales. Rapunzel does not escape her world. The world adjusts around her, unevenly and imperfectly.

Crypting of both the classics

When read alongside Guha's *The Ugly Duckling*, Basu's retelling makes clearer how disabled women's narratives disrupt the conventions of classical fairy tales. In many traditional stories, difference marks a body as provisional or unfinished. Acceptance tends to arrive only after transformation, correction, or rescue. Disability, if it appears at all, often operates as something that must be removed for the story to end properly. Both Kaali and Rapunzel resist this structure. Kaali's story refuses the idea that belonging should depend on bodily change. Rapunzel's narrative refuses the assumption that disabled women need to be saved. In both cases, disability remains present throughout the story. It shapes relationships, decisions, and space rather than disappearing at the moment of resolution. Fairy tales frequently assume a body that moves easily and independently, without naming that assumption. McRuer's idea of compulsory able-bodiedness helps explain how such norms come to feel natural. In these retellings, that naturalness breaks down. Roads do not work. Help is refused. Rescue loses its authority. Able-bodiedness no longer sits quietly in the background.

Time also functions differently in these stories. Neither Kaali nor Rapunzel moves toward a clear endpoint of improvement or normalisation. Kafer's concept of crip time is useful here, not as a framework imposed from outside, but as a way of noticing what the stories already do. Progress is not measured through cure or transformation. Instead, the emphasis falls on recognition, adjustment, and collective change. The stories end, but they do not close neatly. Feminist disability theory draws attention to the overlapping pressures placed on disabled women's bodies. As Susan Wendell argues, disabled women often experience marginalisation through intersecting expectations of gender and ability. These retellings confront that tension directly. Disabled femininity is not disciplined or softened. It is assertive, sometimes uncomfortable, and politically visible. Taken together, these stories do not simply revise familiar fairy tales. They unsettle the assumptions that make those tales work in the first place. Disabled women are not positioned as problems to be fixed or symbols to be interpreted. They are shown acting within the limits of their worlds, pushing against those limits, and altering them, even when the results remain partial and unfinished.

Conclusion

The retellings of *The Ugly Duckling* and *Rapunzel* in *And They Lived... Ever After: Disabled Women Retell Fairy Tales* show how familiar narratives can be reworked when told from disabled perspectives. What changes is not only the plot but the logic that usually governs fairy tales. Rather than repeating the expectation that bodily difference must be corrected, erased, or overcome, these stories linger on difference instead. Disability is not framed as an obstacle to meaning but as something that actively produces it. In doing so, the retellings unsettle deeply embedded ideas about beauty, normalcy, and belonging- ideas that often operate invisibly within cultural storytelling. In Guha's reinterpretation of *The Ugly Duckling*, Kaali's journey does not follow the familiar path toward acceptance through physical transformation. That trajectory is deliberately disrupted. Instead of moving toward bodily conformity, the narrative shifts inward, toward self-recognition. Transformation, if it can be called that, does not occur at the level of appearance. The story draws attention to the harm embedded in narratives that equate worth with visual normality, exposing how such frameworks quietly enforce exclusion. What Kaali gains is not a new body, but a refusal of the terms on which value has traditionally been assigned.

A related refusal appears in Basu's *Rapunzel and the People of Companara*, though it takes a different narrative form. The familiar rescue trope is largely set aside. Rapunzel is not positioned as someone waiting for liberation to arrive from elsewhere.

Her wheelchair, importantly, is not treated as a symbol of confinement or tragedy. It is simply part of her everyday movement through the world. The limitations she encounters emerge instead from social and physical environments that are not designed with her in mind. In this way, the story redirects attention away from the disabled body and toward the structures that produce exclusion in the first place.

When approached through Crip Theory, these retellings can be read as resisting compulsory able-bodiedness and the expectation that narratives must resolve through Kafer's concept of crip futurity; the stories gesture toward futures in which disabled lives are not delayed, deferred, or treated as conditional upon bodily change. Progress here is uneven. Time does not move toward normalisation. Instead, value emerges through interdependence, care, and collective reimagining rather than individual bodily achievement. Seen this way, re-storying becomes more than a literary strategy. It functions as a political intervention. When disabled women rewrite canonical fairy tales, they are not simply revising inherited plots; they are interrupting the cultural scripts that determine whose bodies are granted narrative importance, desire, and care. These retellings stretch the fairy-tale genre itself, opening it to forms of belonging that do not depend on bodily correction or idealised norms of appearance and ability. By centring disabled women's voices and experiences, *And They Lived...Ever After* aligns with a growing body of work that challenges ableist aesthetics within literature. Disability is articulated not as a lack or deviation but as a site of knowledge, creativity, and power. There remains, however, a significant scope for further inquiry. Future research might extend this crip lens to other fairy tales or narrative forms, examining how disability-centred storytelling continues to reshape cultural imaginaries across literature, media and popular culture in complex and ongoing ways.

Author Contributions: All authors have contributed equally to this work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data sharing policy does not apply to this article.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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